

THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC FACTORS ON INTEGRITY OF TEACHERS AT SELECTED SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN OYO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Education is the bedrock of development of any nation, and its integrity is vital for nurturing a culture of transparency, accountability and good governance. Nevertheless, corruption in education weakens the very foundation of this vital sector, promoting inequality, inhibiting socio mobility and compromising the future of individuals and the nations. Several efforts have been made in order to address the issue of corruption in education sector, but it remains a persistent issue, mostly in developing nations. This study examines the complex relationship between socio-economic factors driving corruption and integrity in education. Rational choice theory underpinned; descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Multistage sampling techniques was used to select the respondents. Questionnaire was the instrument used in collection of the data. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. The result revealed that socio-economic factors such poor remuneration, shortage of qualified teacher and socio mobility significantly influence the integrity of teachers. Therefore, socio-economic factors should be improved in order to eradicate corruption and promote integrity among teachers, so as to achieve quality education, academic success, social mobility and to create more equitable and trustworthy education system.

Key words: Social, Economic, Corruption, Integrity and Education.

Introduction

Secondary education serves as the foundational base and connecting bridge upon which all subsequent levels of education are constructed, it serves as the foundation for human capital development in a nation. The importance of education to the development of a nation's human capital cannot be over-emphasized. Therefore, the Nigerian government developed a series of educational policies at the national and state levels. These policies were intended to restructure and revitalize activities throughout the nation's educational system incorporating primary, secondary and university.

Integrity entails being trustworthy, accountable, responsible, and constant in words and actions (Mseti and Kinemo, 2023). The concept of integrity is of utmost importance in the institution of learning. It is the principal pillar of any organization's effectiveness and efficiency. Integrity

comprises characteristics of consistent, considerate, compassionate, transparent, and honest individuals as established in literature.

Due to the government's commitment to education, the government and policymakers expect that the investment in education will produce high-quality secondary school graduates, skillful students, and transparent school administrators and teachers. However, these remarkable expectations have remained a dream over the years. The reason behind this is that corruption has had negative impact on the education sector, challenging its integrity and undermine the value of academic integrity. Corruption is any act committed in a public, private or corporate organization involving the exchange of money or gift items, signing of signatures, immoral acts, or any other activity which harms society, for personal or group gain. Dishonesty has turn into an unavoidable immoral in society today, which cuts across all sectors and serves as a major barrier to the economic growth of the nation.

An aspect of corruption in the education sector is the inappropriate behaviour of individuals in positions of authority. They do this to obtain personal gain which is detrimental to the standard of education and national advancement (Edinoh, Saidu, and Okpunukpang, 2024). This study reveals various expressions of corruption in the education sector which include government or regulatory corruption, embezzlement of school funds, leaking of examination questions and answers, cheating in examinations, unauthorized change in students' grades, bribery for admission, falsification of students records, and pressure by parents on teachers for grade inflation (Akinniyi, Erinsakin, and Emma-Ayire, 2021). Self-interest compromises the education sector's integrity; therefore, leading to erosion of standards in the education sector. All these show that the stakeholders in the education sector need collaborative efforts to tackle this great menace.

According to Bamigbola (2019), corruption in education applies to all institutions of learning in the 36 states of the federation. It undermines the quality of education and limits access to it. This study will be limited to Oyo State, which is known as the pacesetter for better learning and quality education. Despite the importance of secondary education, accessing quality education and ethical standards within this level of the educational system is shaped by socio-economic factors. Socio-economic factors have an impact on corruption and integrity within the secondary level of the educational system. These factors range from poverty and income inequality to a lack of resources, political effects, and cultural values; creating a multifaceted environment where corruption increases (Wails & Uche, 2023).

In June 2021, 13 head teachers and two assistant head teachers were suspended by the state government for mismanaging the grants given to their schools by the State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB, 2021). In 2022, the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) delisted 50 secondary schools in Oyo State. The schools were delisted because of various degrees of examination malpractices, which is corruption in education. Though the state government frowned at this by demoting the educational officers who were found guilty, they were later reinstated after several interventions.

Also, on 12 October 2024, the chairman of the Teaching Service Commission of Oyo State (TESCOM), Pastor Akinade Alamu, cleared the air about the request for bribes from the public during their recruitment exercise. Requesting bribes before offering employment to teachers is also a form of corruption in the education sector. Therefore, there is a need for prompt action to combat this menace to prevent the total collapse of the education system by corruption. The Oyo State Government, on the 18th of July, 2023, announced through the TESCOM chairman, the enforcement of the examination malpractice act, as enshrined in Nigeria's 1999 constitution; the punishment is three years in jail or a fine of ₦100,000 (TESCOM, 2023). This announcement was made as a result of several reports of both parents' and students' involvement in examination malpractice. In this study, it was discovered that there are several unauthorized sites online where students pay to access external examination questions with prepared answers. All these are corrupt practices in the education sector.

Several socioeconomic factors promote corruption and reduce integrity in the educational establishments. They comprise poor salary for staff and teachers, inadequate professional teachers, poverty, poor funding and limited resources, unemployment, economic inequality among students and communities, cultural norms, and the lack of social mobility and opportunities (Edinoh, Saidu, and Okpunukpang, 2024).

Remuneration is the total package paid for the service rendered or work done by an individual. Poor remuneration for teachers is a major socio-economic factor that influences corruption in secondary education in the state. According to Bolanle (2023), remuneration predicts the quality of education. The total package of an Oyo State teacher is very low. A level-15 officer who is at the administrative level is earning ₦270,000 (TESCOM, 2024) after serving for 24 years. Interactions during this study show that the cost of transportation to schools is not less

than ₦95,000 per month; leaving stipends for teachers to take care of themselves and their families.

This, coupled with the poor economic situation of the country has made teachers unable to meet their daily demands, resulting in frustration, emotional trauma, and corruption. Poor remuneration leads to corruption according to (Idonije, Timothy, Usman, Haruna, and Umar, 2022). Corruption in education reduces the quality of teaching and the quality of students' learning outcomes, resulting in a poor global image of the education system. It led to understaffing in some schools, a stall in the development, and dropouts from schools.

The lack of professional teachers is another socio-economic factor that affects the education sector. Teaching is a profession which requires expertise, but it is quite unfortunate that some teachers in secondary schools are not professionals. This influences qualitative delivery in schools negatively. Due to the high unemployment rate in the country, some graduates take up teaching as a stepping stone to a better offer, not because they are interested. That is why they leave as soon as a better opportunity comes. Therefore, the teaching ethics, code of conduct, and the virtues of teaching such as honesty, integrity, fairness, trustworthiness, empathy, and practical wisdom are almost missing in the education sector. All these contribute to corruption in the sector.

Bolanle and Ayeni (2023), averred that due to a lack of proficient teachers in the state, corps members, whether trained or not, are being deployed in their thousands as teachers to secondary schools. This has led to poor delivery and opened the doors to all sorts of ill practices that are unethical. Asiyai (2020) posited that a shortage of qualified teachers leads to corruption, which reduces the quality of education, teaching and learning, quality of students, and learning output. Furthermore, lack of adequate funding is another crucial socio-economic factor that causes corruption in secondary schools in Oyo State. Funding in education is the financial support given to schools to enhance the achievement of a qualitative education system. Funding is important because it is the driver of the sector. Shortage of funds for secondary education has led to corruption in the education system, and this has resulted in a decline in the quality of teaching and learning, and the quality of students' learning outcomes as established in literature. This is the reason why some of the secondary school graduates are referred to as half-baked graduates. Inadequate funding has led to a lack of instructional materials, inadequate infrastructural facilities, and in the long run, poor quality education.

Also, infrastructural facilities in schools are important in the achievement of educational goals. Proper infrastructures aid academic success of students and teachers. They provide a favourable working environment for educators and help the learners to learn successfully. Despite the fact that facilities play a crucial role in the achievement of educational goals, most post-primary schools in the state are faced with shortages. This shortage problem has been linked to corruption in the educational system, according to Ogunode and Johnson (2021).

Social mobility is another socio-economic factor that leads to corruption in secondary education. Socio-economic mobility in education is the ability of individuals, particularly from poor backgrounds, to improve their socio-economic status through education. The downward turn of social mobility contributes to vice in the educational institution. It manifests in the following ways: desperation, inequalities, pressure to succeed, and lack of opportunities according to different literature.

Inequality in wealth distribution influences corruption in the education sector. In a situation where, the wealth discrepancy between the upper and lower socio-economic strata is persistent corruption abounds. Prevalent and prolonged lack, tremendously high levels of material deprivation and severe disparities in the allocation of resources, are major causes of corruption in Nigeria. Ogaziechi (2021) posited that Nigeria has been characterised as the global epicentre of poverty. Indicating that there is mass poverty in the nation regardless of the abundant natural resources that are accessible in it. This is a major factor influencing corruption in secondary schools. The economic situation of the state has resulted in downward social mobility of all the citizens.

Irrespective of regular payment of salaries, teachers are not exempted because the awful inflation in the nation has placed a big economic weight on them. As gathered in this study, the majority of teachers find it difficult to eat three square meals daily and fulfil other financial obligations. Therefore, to meet their pressing needs, corrupt practices such as extortion, favouritism of students and many more creep in. The general effect of economic hardship in the nation has resulted in instructors engaging themselves in vices such as beguile admission seekers, unlawful financial extraction, and squeezing money from students' parents (Erunke, 2019). Against this backdrop, this study proposes to investigate the influence of socio-economic factors on integrity of teachers in secondary education in Oyo State.

Statement of the Problem

Corrupt activities are evident in all sectors in the country and the education sector is not exempted; especially teaching and learning practices, use of education resources, and development of education policies. There have been several studies on tertiary institutions and public offices, but studies of corruption at the secondary level of education are relatively few. That is the reason why this study intends to investigate the influence of socio-economic factors on integrity of teachers in secondary education in Oyo State. It is on the backdrop that this study seeks to examine socio-economic factors influencing corruption and integrity in secondary education in Oyo State.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of academic integrity in post primary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of corruption in post primary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria?
3. What is the level of socioeconomic status of educators in post primary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

H₀₁ Social economic factors do not have a significant influence on the academic integrity of educators in post primary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria.

H₀₂ Social economic factors do not have a significant influence on the corruption of teachers in secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Attah, Bada and Haruna (2019), conducted research on corruption and its effect on the socio-economic growth of Nigeria. The result revealed that corruption is rampant in every sector of the country. Therefore, it has a negative effect on the national development of the nation. It was recommended that courses on corruption should be included in the school curriculum at every level of education.

Edimoh, Saidu and Okpunukpang (2024), explored the effects of corruption and education in Nigeria, it was established that shortage of infrastructural facilities, instructional materials, poor funding, inadequate professional teachers and poor quality of education are negative effects of corruption on education. Other researchers such as Kirya, (2019), Ngatia, Njoka, and

Ndegwa, (2019), Saidu, and Micah, 2020, Ogunode, and Johnson (2021), Mseti and Kinemo,(2023),Obona, Erim and Njan, (2023) established that corruption is endemic to education sector therefore there is need to promote integrity.

Bolanle and Ayeni (2023), carried out study on parental influences on quality of education in Oyo State. The investigation addressed three critical research questions while three hypothesis were postulated and answered. The research design was descriptive in nature. It was established that quality of education is low in Oyo State. Also, that parental factors predicts quality education. It was recommended that parents should provide adequate learning materials for their children in other to achieve quality education.

Theoretical Framework

The framework of this study anchored on rational choice theory (RCT), it was propounded by Adam Smith in 1776. It proposes that personalities make rational choice based on their self-interest, considering the potential cost and benefits. This theory explains how socio-economic factors such as poor remuneration, shortage of teachers, limited career advancement opportunities can influence teacher's decision to compromise their integrity. Therefore, the relevance of this theory is that it provides a framework for understanding how teachers might consider the cost and benefits of engaging in corrupt practices and how socio-economic factors might influence their decision making.

Methodology

The investigation employed a descriptive research design using a survey methodology. Survey research enables only a sample to be studied, after which generalisation could be made. The study was carried out in Oyo State, Nigeria. Nested sampling procedure was used to select three local government areas from the three geo-political zones, where 18 schools were selected. The total population was six hundred and twelve (612), but one hundred and twenty (120) respondents were randomly selected. One hundred and eight questionnaires were retrieved, representing 90%, which is adequate for generalisation. The study employed descriptive statistics and inferential statistics.

Discussion of Findings

1. What is the level of academic integrity in post primary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria?

	Very High	High	Low	Very Low	Mean	S.D.	Remark
Academic integrity in teaching is very important.	0 0.0%	2 1.9%	24 22.2%	82 75.9%	3.74	.481	Very High
Ethical behaviour should always be emphasised in the classroom	4 3.7%	2 1.9%	30 27.8%	72 66.7%	3.57	.713	Very High
Integrity should be a valued cultural practice in the school.	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	30 27.8%	78 72.2%	3.72	.450	Very High
Recognition should be given to promoters of integrity	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	30 27.8%	78 72.2%	3.72	.450	Very High
				Weighted Mean	3.69		Very High

The result showed that the level of academic integrity in postprimary schools in Oyo State is very high with a weighted mean average of 3.69. This is evident in the responses of the research participants, indicating high integrity awareness among school constituents.

2. What is the level of corruption in post primary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria?

	Very High	High	Low	Very Low	Mean	S.D.	Remark
Preferential treatment to certain students exists in the school	12 11.1%	46 42.6%	37 34.3%	13 12.0%	2.47	.848	Low
Corruption is becoming part of school administration.	3 2.8%	27 25.0%	52 48.1%	26 24.1%	2.94	.777	High
Falsifying students' grades and records is becoming the norm in the school setting.	11 10.2%	29 26.9%	40 37.0%	28 25.9%	2.79	.948	High
Corruption in the system is affecting student learning outcomes.	5 4.6%	17 15.7%	48 44.4%	38 35.2%	3.10	.831	High
Extortion and bribery are becoming the new normal in the system.	13 12.0%	32 29.6%	54 50.0%	9 8.3%	2.55	.813	High
External authorities are available to report corrupt practices.	6 5.6%	39 36.1%	52 48.1%	11 10.2%	2.63	.744	High
				Weighted Mean	2.75		High

The study showed that the level of corruption in post primary schools in Oyo State is high, with a weighted mean of 2.72. This is a result of responses from the respondents admitting that corruption is affecting students' learning outcomes, among others.

3. What is the level of socioeconomic status of educators in post primary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria?

	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	S.D.	Remark
Low salary affects the discharge of duties.	6 5.6%	10 9.3%	51 47.2%	41 38.0%	3.18	.818	High
Inadequate resources allocated to schools have an impact on quality delivery. (Funding)	0 0.0%	2 1.9%	37 34.3%	69 63.9%	3.62	.524	Very High

Professional development training attracts favouritism to some extent.	3	17	68	20	2.97	.676	High
Economic instability affects teaching and learning activities(negative socio-mobility)	0	2	51	55	3.49	.538	High
	2.8%	15.7%	63.0%	18.5%			
	0.0%	1.9%	47.2%	50.9%			
					Weighted Mean	3.32	High

The findings showed that the socio-economic status of Oyo State teachers is very low. That was the reason why the resultant effects such as inability to discharge duties, poor quality delivery, and negative social mobility of the teachers were very high.

Socioeconomic factors do not have a significant influence on the Academic Integrity of educators in post primary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	24.350	1	24.350	12.945	.000 ^b
	Residual	199.391	106	1.881		
	Total	223.741	107			

R = 0.330^a

R Square = 0.109

Adjusted R Square = 0.100

Std. Error of the Estimate = 1.37151

Socioeconomic factors have a significant influence on the academic integrity of educators in post primary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. The study revealed a statistically significant relationship with a p-value of 0.000, providing strong evidence that socioeconomic factors influenced the integrity of teachers.

Social economic factors do not have a significant influence on the corruption of instructors in post primary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	81.100	1	81.100	9.575	.003 ^b
	Residual	897.816	106	8.470		
	Total	978.917	107			

R = 0.288^a

R Square = 0.083

Adjusted R Square = 0.074

Std. Error of the Estimate = 2.91032

Socio-economic factors lead to corruption of teachers in secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. This result showed a statistically significant association with a p-value of 0.003, providing strong evidence that socioeconomic factors influenced corruption among teachers. Low-level remuneration has been established to have a great influence on corruption and integrity from the study. This study is in line with (Edinoh, Saidu, and Okpunukpang, 2024; Idonije, Timothy, Usman, Haruna and Umar, 2022; Akinniyi, Erinsakin and Emma-Ayire, 2021). Therefore, the state government should increase the remuneration of secondary school teachers, so that teachers will be able to meet their basic needs. This will reduce the pressure exerted by economic constraints. It will also move teachers away from the poverty threshold. Consequently, it will shift the education sector's reputation from corrupt and ineffective to trustworthy and effective.

Furthermore, the study revealed that a shortage of qualified teachers in secondary education significantly influenced corruption and integrity. It was noted from these findings that the lack of qualified teachers gave room for the engagement of untrained personnel (corps members) in education, which led to a mismatch in the teaching profession. This study is in line with (Bolanle, 2023 and Akinniyi, Erinsatin, and Emma-Ayire, 2021). This study supports Edimoh, Saidu and Okpunukpang (2024), to propose that funding is important in the education sector. If it is adequately provided, there will be a sufficient supply of personnel and non-personnel. This will lead to the reduction or elimination of corruption and promote integrity.

It was established by this finding that social mobility can negatively influence corruption and integrity in secondary schools. This study is in line with Onyido and Duru (2019). Therefore, it is required that the government should come up with good policies which will alleviate poverty among the populace. The results also showed that there is a positive influence of the socio-economic factors on the integrity or corruption of teachers in secondary schools in Oyo State.

Conclusion

Education in Nigeria generally has been vulnerable to several challenges, corruption is prominent among others. The impacts of this hazard on the state of the educational institution is so obvious that virtually every section of the sector feels it. Therefore, this study identified the causes of corruption and its effects on the educational system at the state level. The determinants of corruption in the education sector include low salary packages or poor remuneration, shortage of qualified teachers, poor funding and negative social mobility of teachers. The pervasive impact of corruption revealed through this research are low quality of education, poor facilities, and an uncondusive environment for teaching and learning. Based on these negative effects, some recommendations were made. They will help to promote integrity in the educational institution in the state if implementation is comprehensive.

The study concludes that socio-economic factors can influence the integrity and corruption of teachers in post primary schools in Oyo State.

Recommendations

The findings of this study underpin the following recommendations:

- To promote integrity in the teaching profession, the socio-economic status of teachers should be taken into consideration when formulating strategies and policies for enhancing the quality of education.
- Teachers' salaries should be reviewed upward at regular intervals so that the teachers will perform optimally.
- Adequate funding and proper monitoring should be embarked upon to provide adequate educational materials for qualitative secondary education in the state.
- Only educationists should be recruited as teachers. Untrained teachers should not be recruited as teachers. Teaching is a profession; therefore, it requires professionals.
- External examination bodies should put adequate security measures in place to stop the leakages of questions with prepared answers before the commencement of examinations.

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